

PRESS RELEASE

The EU Project GRAPHERGIA Launches 3 Demonstration Cases to Pilot Graphene-Based Energy Solutions

Patras, 31 March 2026 - The European research project GRAPHERGIA has officially launched the piloting phase of its [three demonstration cases](#) implementing **graphene-based technologies for energy harvesting and storage** in real-life applications. The demonstrators' development began in March 2026 and aims to validate cutting-edge solutions in **smart self-charging textiles** and **next-generation lithium-ion batteries** for applications in **healthcare, aerospace, mobility, and wearable electronics**.

Three Demonstrators Enter Piloting Phase

The first demonstrator, '**All-in-one self-charging textile capable of energy harvesting and storage**', is led by [BORN Knitting Engineers](#). It integrates advanced electronic components directly into fabrics, enabling battery-free wearable solutions supporting wellness and performance monitoring. Two use cases are being explored: a **smart textile system featuring a T-shirt designed for energy harvesting and storage** and a **belt for real-time gait monitoring**, together with a self-powered **smart seating** prototype that will function as an autonomous **passenger seat indicator**.

The second demonstrator, '**Self-powered structurally integrated sensor for aerospace structures**', is guided by [Adamant Composites](#). It focuses on a self-powered, miniaturised sensor embedded within composite materials powered by a triboelectric nanogenerator. This system will **enable wireless monitoring of strain and temperature**, providing continuous insight into **material performance during operation**.

[Pleione Energy](#) leads the third demonstrator, '**Advanced graphene-based LIB module prototype for space applications**', supporting the development of a rigorous qualification protocol for cylindrical LIB cells, ensuring both electrochemical performance and mechanical integrity **for integration to CubeSat missions**. The module will comprise battery cells, a management system, interconnectors, and supporting structures, and will be prepared for in-orbit validation and future use in space applications.

*"The launch of our three demonstrators marks a **crucial step for GRAPHERGIA as it moves forward with system-level validation, generating key performance data to confirm readiness for***

integration into textile, aerospace, and space-grade energy applications”, explains **Despoina Batsouli**, Head of Advanced Materials Division at **Adamant Composites**, the GRAPHERGIA partner leading and coordinating the demo cases.

Eco-Design and Sustainability at the Core of GRAPHERGIA's Methodology

A central element of the project is its **Safe-and-Sustainable-by-Design (SSbD)** approach. GRAPHERGIA employs water-based or solvent-free materials, avoids hazardous substances such as toxic binders, and uses laser-based processes to **reduce energy consumption and waste**.

The project also incorporates **Life Cycle Assessment (LCA)** and **Life Cycle Costing (LCC)** to **evaluate environmental and economic performance**. These assessments examine the full process chain, from material development to manufacturing and deployment. In addition, **eco-design principles are applied to enhance the recyclability and reusability** of all materials and components developed within the project.

About GRAPHERGIA: Powering Future Energy with Graphene

[GRAPHERGIA](#) is a **Horizon Europe** research and innovation project part of the [Graphene Flagship](#), powering future energy with graphene. It brings together eleven academic and industrial partners from six European countries under the Greek leadership of the **Foundation for Research and Technology – Hellas (FORTH)**.

The consortium also includes [Pleione Energy GmbH](#) (Germany); [Adamant Composites Ltd.](#) (Greece); [Université Gustave Eiffel](#) (France); [Born GmbH Knitwear for Fashion and Engineering](#) (Germany); [Università degli Studi de Roma La Sapienza](#) (Italy); [Comsensus, DOO](#) (Slovenia); [Deutsches Zentrum für Luft - Und Raumfahrt EV](#) (Germany); [Next Technology Tecnotessile](#) (Italy); [AUSTRALO Interinnov Marketing Lab SL](#) (Spain); and [Euglottia I.K.E.](#) (Greece).

DEMO CASES FOR GRAPHENE-BASED ENERGY SOLUTIONS

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